

Man by Rabindranath Tagore: Journey for Philosophy of Gerontology

Dr. Ryo Takahashi, Specially Appointed Professor, Health Sciences of Hokkaido, Hokkaido, Japan.

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-8817-1377>

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13840549

Abstract

The purpose of the paper is to introduce Sir Rabindranath Tagore's (1861-1941) universal contribution through his lectures. There are a few papers about Tagore, but no papers about this topic "MAN", at all from 2015- 2023. The main method used in writing this study was a literature review of online and offline media sources, assisted by qualitative research methodology through interviews. Prior research on the field has not been investigated. My research is originally Lectures at Andhra University when President Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan was vice chancellor at Andhra University from 1931 to 1936. this paper found that These lectures give teaching the foundation for the philosophy of gerontology and the origins of human education. I recommended readers conduct research for effective education for all ages from children to aged so that this understanding has an impact on society and benefits researchers, and educators involved in the study. In future studies, it might include comprehensive descriptions of approaches for using various ways to further education and research studies.

Keywords: Rabindranath Tagore, Andhra University, Care-Fit, Gerontology, Philosophy.

What is the Philosophy of Gerontology? You may find the top on Google by just typing Gerontology and Philosophy as The Historical Philosophy of Gerontology in the Context of Our Future (Takahashi & Shibata 2019)

1) When you want to learn more about the Philosophy of Gerontology, you can go forward to read the title Philosophy of Gerontology (Takahashi 2019 a)

2) Moreover, if you want to learn more relationship between Gerontology and Science with Philosophy, you can read from The Science, Philosophy and Bioethics of Gerontology: An Individual and Community Journey from Japan (Takahashi 2019 b)

3) Finally, if you want to learn about philosophical understanding of Man with Bioethical understanding, you can learn from MAN: A Study on the Philosophical Edification of Zanshin in Bushido Context of Future (Takahashi 2022)

4) Finally, we have developed our philosophy of Gerontology. That is why Tagore's Book is very helpful for creating our own philosophical life. This book explores Man: A Study on the Philosophical Edification of Zanshin in the Bushido Context of the Future. This study is focused on finding the context of the edification of Zanshin. To edify means to instruct and improve, especially in moral and religious knowledge. Zanshin (Japanese: 残心) means the state of awareness with relaxed alertness which is generally used in Japanese martial arts, especially Kendo. A literal Japanese translation of Zanshin is "remaining mind". Zanshin is originally used for all Japanese culture's life including Kado, Sado, Judo, Kendo, Kyudo, Shogido, etc. We were introduced to "The Historical Philosophy of Gerontology in the Context of Our Future" (Takahashi & Shibata 2022)

5). This paper was introduced through Tagore's lectures about Man. Rabindranath Tagore (1861-1941) was the first Asian person to receive the Nobel Prize in 1913. He is

highly respected as an Indian poet, thinker, educator, artist and screenwriter. He is known as the lyricist and composer of the Indian and Bangladeshi anthems, and for establishing an open-air school (now Vishva Bharati National University) in Shantinikhetan, about three hours by train from Calcutta in 1901.

6) After the International Conference on Gerontology held at Andhra University in 2009, I visited Tagore House in Calcutta. At that time, I suddenly received inspiration in the room where Tagore and Andhra University were related. Later, one of the books purchased at a used bookstore stated that Tagore had given a special lecture at the Andhra University on December 8-10, 1933.

7) Tagore also has a deep connection with Japan. In particular, through friendship with Tenshin Okakura and Kanpo Arai, starting in 1916, philosophy, art, and educational exchanges were held during five visits to Japan, which led to educational and cultural exchanges between India and Japan. Tagore's welcome when he came to Japan after winning the first Nobel Prize in Asia was amazing. However, when Tagore sincerely warned against the Westernizing Japan situation, few Japanese people at that time listened.

8) Tagore wrote as follows: The road is ever extended to the outside and has no meaning within itself. Its significance is reached when it reaches the home where begins the manifestation of the inward. When the course of evolution advanced to the stage of man its character changed, it shifted its emphasis mainly from the body to the mind. There is relentless competition among them, where creatures struggle to preserve their physical integrity.

9) Picture 1

Picture 1: Manuscript of Man

This teaches the life process of Man. Gerontology is a science of human philosophy. In other words, it can be said to be an applied practical science that uses various methods to explore how humans live. The origin of the word gerontology can be traced to Ilya Metchnikoff's 1903 book "The Nature of Man: Studies in Optimistic Philosophy".

Metchnikoff is generally known as a microbiologist and zoologist, but at the basis of his research, he founded religious and philosophical ideas from a variety of perspectives, as well as various languages and cultures. When people approach research holistically and discover their true goals in life and science, they can unite toward a single ideal (Metchnikoff, 1903). Aiming for this ideal, the authors have been aiming for a renaissance of gerontology under the title “Da Vinci Awareness Project 2012”. As part of this effort, the International General Conference on Gerontology was held at Andhra University in India in 2009. The author’s encounter with Tagore began on October 13, 2008, when I visited the shop of Mr. Girida Chi, a party rental shop, on the way home from yoga. (Picture 2) Mr. Chi was interested in the history of Japan and told me about how the seafarers kindly treated him when a Japanese trading ship was coming to Visakhapatnam when he was a child. So, I was introduced to Ms. Rani Mayank Kumari Deo (President of the Rotary Club of Visakhapatnam), who is a friend of the King of Jyepore and is a direct descendant of the royal family ^(Note 2).

Picture 2: Mr. Girida Chi & Ms. Rani Mayank Kumari Deo

Tagore also visited Visakhapatnam and was shown a scrap of photographs taken with the then rector, Radhakrishnan, but I did not know what the purpose of coming to Andhra University was. A search for Tagore’s lecture at the Andhra University revealed that a book had been published in 1937 under the title “MAN”.¹⁰ The description on page 75 of the book reads: “This book contains three lectures given at Andhra University in 1933. The first lecture, “Man”, is about the eternal person in each individual. The second lecture is about “the immediate object of the most intimate awareness” and “the superior person who inspires people after perfection”. The last chapter, “I am He,” is about the divine man in our thoughts and actions.” Dr. Tagore was invited to the University because of his connection with the second rector, Radhakrishnan (the second president of India after the first vice president), who was involved in philosophical research and teaching not only in India but also in Cambridge.⁵) When Tagore prepared for this lecture in 1933, 20 years after he won the Nobel Prize, he was already 72 years old. In a letter on September 23, 1932, President Radhakrishnan thanked Tagore for the invitation but felt the limitations of his health due to his busy daily life and old age. However, President Radhakrishnan sent a letter of request stating that he would like to request that this request be not just a message to students, but a message that will remain for future generations. This was realized and exists as a book called

“Man”. Researching Tagore's lectures at Andhra University revealed that he had visited Visakhapatnam, the home of Andhra University twice in 1933 and 1934, the first time at Andhra University (8, 9, and 10 December 1933), and the second time with the Jepur Maharaja to request support for the university run by Tagore. He asked Elder Korul Jakandaha Rao, who is familiar with the history of the area, to find out more. Mr. Rao gave Tagore a copy of a magazine article and photographs about his visit to Andhra University. He then asked Kondepuri Suba Rao, 94 years old and editor-in-chief of a Telugu language magazine, to find the source of the photo. (Picture 3)

Picture 3: Mr. Korul Jakandaha Rao

The author was able to find Mr. Marty's address from a list of past subscribers. So I immediately contacted him and went out, and although he was away the first time, a neighbour told me that On my second visit, I met the wife of Mr. Marty's son and saw the same picture as the magazine framed on it. On my third visit, I was able to meet Mr. Caridas, Mr. Marty's son, and hear his valuable story. When Tagore visited Andhra University. Mr. Marty, the most trusted student at Andhra University was entrusted with watching over the accommodation. (Picture 4)

Picture 4: Mr & Mrs. Caridas & Mr. Marty's Son

On the last day, Mr. Marty was always at the door of his room, and when Tagore asked him when he was resting, he replied, “Master, I am not going home and I am playing

my role here,” to which Tagore replied, “I have never seen such a faithful student, I will listen to your wishes, what do you want?” “I would appreciate it if you could take a photo with the Vice Chancellor.” (Picture 5; Note 1)

Picture 5: Mr. Tagore with associates

Picture 6: Mr. Tagore & Dr. Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan

Mr. D.V.S.H. Marty (1912-2008) made a lifelong contribution to society as an educator and as the first Boy Scout Master in Andhra Pradesh¹¹) (Picture 7)

Picture 7: Mr. D. V. S. H. Marty

I met with Ms. Rao Andra and she told me about when she was only 4 years old. Dr. Rao's father, Prof. Seilsuan Chand, was a professor at the Faculty of Philosophy at that time. (Picture 8)

Picture 8: Ms. Rao Andra

When the author visited the home of Jaipur Maharaj, who was a student at the Visva-Bharati University, and when I led the students from Santiniketan, where the Visva-Bharati University is located, to perform a drama, the students of Andhra University made a long and noisy presentation in Bengali. Tagore, who was sitting on the stage indignantly at the situation, made a bright red face and immediately cancelled the presentation of the students

and dismissed them. President Radhakrishnan apologized on behalf of the university. He recalled things he remembered clearly. Based on these experiences, the author went to Kolkata on June 3, 2009, to conduct further research on “MAN” at a university in Tagore, and the next day he took a train to Santiniketan. Professor Mohit Chakrabarti and Mr. Nilanjan Banerjee of the Tagore Museum. (Picture 9)

Picture 9: Mr. Niranjan Baberjee

Conclusion

For the author, the encounter with Tagore’s “MAN person”¹² has become an eternal treasure that lays the foundation for the philosophy of gerontology and teaches us the origins of human education. From now on, the author hopes to work hard at my studies to be involved in education that allows people to discover their consciousness and sense of values which is called Kigatsuku mind in Japanese.

References

- [1] Takahashi Ryo & Shibata Hiroshi. “The Historical Philosophy of Gerontology in the Context of Our Future.” *HSOA Journal of Gerontology & Geriatric Medicine*, 5, 2019, pp. 1-26.
- [2] Takahashi, Ryo. *Philosophy of Gerontology*, Ryo Takahashi Study Lab, Sendai University, 2019a, pp. 1-180.
- [3] Takahashi, Ryo. *The Science, Philosophy and Bioethics of Gerontology: An Individual and Community Journey from Japan*. Lap Lambert Academic Publishing, 2019b.
- [4] Takahashi Ryo, *MAN: A Study on the Philosophical Edification of Zanshin in Bushido Context of Future*. BAYSHOP (Generis Publishing), 2022 .
- [5] Agatsuma Kazuo. *Tagore - Poetry, Thought, Life*. Reitaku University Press, 2006.
- [6] The Calcutta Municipal Corporation. *The Calcutta Municipal Gazette Tagore Memorial Supplement*, 1941
- [7] Kakuyama Yoshihiro. *Tagore and Warnings to Japan*. Collection of Papers Commemorating the 100th Anniversary of Tagore's Birth, Tagore Memorial Society,

- 1961, pp. 271-282.
- [8] Tagore, R. *Man, lectured delivered at the Andhra University Under the terms of the Sir Alladi Krishnaswamy Endowment*, Huxley Press, 1937.
- [9] Sarvepalli, G. *Radhakrishnan A Biography*. Oxford University Press, 1989, pp. 120-144.
- [10] Marty, D.V.S.N. *Brief History of Scout Activities and Special Meritorious Activities of Senior Most Scout Master in Andhra Pradesh*. 2nd Southern Region Mini Jamboree 5th-9th, December, 2006.
- [11] Tagore, R. MAN, In R. Takahashi (Tran.), Honnoizumisha, 2011.

Notes:

Note 1: Sarvepalli Radhakrishnan, (September 5, 1888 - April 17, 1975) was born in Tamil, southern India. He is known as an Indian educator, philosopher, and politician. His birthday, September 5th, is observed as Teacher's Day throughout India. After graduating from the Madras Christian College, he earned a degree in philosophy and religion from Oxford University. As for his involvement with Andhra University, he has been giving lectures to students since its founding in 1927. Second in 1931 on a five-year contract deputy president. For more information, visit SarvepalliGopal (1989): A Biography See Radhakrishnan, Oxford University Press, pp.120-144. Afterwards, he became president of Benares Hindu University (1939-48) and professor at Oxford University (1936-52). After India became independent, he served as ambassador to the Soviet Union (1949-52), first vice president (1952-62), and was later elected as second president (1962-1967). It will be done. (Written by Shimaiwa: Yahoo Encyclopedia.

Note 2: Jyepore's genealogy Beach, M.C & Singh II, R.N.(2005) Bagta andChokha Master Artists at Devgarh, Artibus Asia epublisher and Deo, Kumar Bidyadhan Singh, JEYPORE (1939): Nandapur(A Forsaken Kingdon), The Utkal Sahitya press.

Author (s) Contribution Statement: Nil

Author (s) Acknowledgement: Nil

Author (s) Declaration: I declare that there is no competing interest in the content and authorship of this scholarly work.

The content of the article is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution4.0 International License.